

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene in Pakistan: An Assessment of the Support of the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank (2000-2016)

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Abstract *An effective Water Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) is considered as one of the building blocks for the health of a populace. Unfortunately, this sector in Pakistan is quite fragile, and the intensity of fragility varies from one unit of the state to the other. However, for the development of WASH in Pakistan, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the World Bank (WB) are providing assistance in project preparation and implementation. This paper outlines the causes of the poor condition of WASH sector in Pakistan. Moreover, it evaluates the interventions of the ADB and the WB in the country from 2000-2016. It is also pondered over whether or not these interventions have brought betterment in WASH sector in different provinces of Pakistan. More importantly, the paper also highlights loopholes in the developmental strategies of ADB and WB and suggests few possible strategies for the development of the WASH sector.*

Introduction

The term “WASH” is a combination of water, sanitation, and hygiene. The word “water” in this term refers to the supply of adequate and quality water to inhabitants of any state. Sanitation means a proper system for disposing of wastewater and feces. About term “WASH” hygiene explains knowledge about techniques and practices that can lead to good health by preventing diseases through cleanliness. Water supply is a basic component of life while better services of water supply and sanitation are essential for human health and are also determinants of a country’s development. Several international conferences had emphasized the importance of water as a basic human right. In 1977, the United Nations (UN) in water conference

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recognized that 'All peoples, whatever is their stage of socio-economic development have the right of access to drinking water according to their need. In addition, the water supply as a human right, water, and sanitation also have social and economic importance. This fact is highlighted in 1992 in an international conference on water and sustainable development in Dublin. According to the 4th principle of this conference 'Water has an economic value in all its competing uses and should be recognized as an economic good' (World Meteorological Organization (WMO), 1992). It means that as a basic right of human being, every individual should have access to water and sanitation services at reasonable price. The three components of WASH sector are interdependent on each other. For example, on the one hand, without better sanitation system it is impossible to keep drinking water safe from contamination of feces and wastewater. While of the other, hygiene is part of water and sanitation, where proper water and sanitation facilities are vital for human health at the same time, improvement in human health cannot be achieved without hygienic behavior.

WASH sector is crucial for a country's socio-economic development, progress in this sector sparks human capital and improvement in human capital paves the way for the development of a country. Whatever amount is spent on the improvement of WASH by a polity, this sector will pay it back in the form of healthy human capital. The availability of WASH services cuts down expenditures on the health sector, both, directly and indirectly. Better quality of drinking water and sanitation services reduces diseases such as diarrhea, typhoid, hepatitis and worm infestation, and in this way financial burden on the health system is reduced. Secondly, availability of tap water at the doorstep for drinking and other household purposes secures time for children and woman who spend most of their time in water fetching. These secured hours can be used for other activities such as ventures for the enhancement knowledge and skills through formal and informal schooling, and overtime at workplaces which can improve earning of the family directly and that of the state indirectly. Provision of water, sanitation and hygiene facilities is the responsibility of the state, however, when a state has no adequate resources to meet the needs of its inhabitants, the international community has a moral obligation to step-in for the assistance of the deficient state in such a scenario and help its people in achieving a better living standard.

WASH in Pakistan

Pakistan is a developing country in the South Asian region having a territory of 796.1 thousand sq. km, and this area is divided into four provinces along with federally administered areas and capital territory. It has a rising population of 207.77 million and among this population, almost 63% live in rural areas and the rest is residing in urban areas (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017). A survey carried out by WB in 2016 had revealed that almost 29.5% population of the

country do not enjoy basic rights and is categorized as underprivileged (poor) inhabitants of the state (World Bank, 2017).

Pakistan has three types of drinking water resources: underground water, surface water, and rainfall. Indus water and its tributaries are the main sources of surface water and reservoirs of groundwater mainly found in Indus Plain, which starts from the foothills of Himalaya and ends at the Arabian sea (Kahlowan & Majeed, 2003). According to an estimate, the groundwater extraction rate of Pakistan in 2010 was 64.82 km per year and among this extraction, the country is using 6% for the domestic purpose (ADB, 2016). Instead of being the 4th largest water extractor, Pakistan has only 30 days water storage capacity, and 16 million Pakistanis have no access to adequate drinking water. In addition, 68 million people in the country have no facility of sanitation. Inadequate water and sanitation services are one of the major causes of diarrheal disease, and due to this disease, 19,000 children under the age of 5 years die each year in Pakistan (WaterAid, 2017).

The major cause of the poor state of affairs in this sector is underfunding. For instance, in the budget of 2017-18 only Rs. 12,500 million and Rs. 1,141 million was allocated for clean drinking water supply and wastewater management respectively (Ministry of Finance, 2017). Moreover, there is a visible discrimination between rural and urban areas regarding investment in this sector. Urban areas, which are already enjoying better water and sanitation facilities and better hygiene, have a larger share in the WASH's funds, as compared to the rural areas which are backward in WASH sector.

Frequent power outages is also one of the causes of the shortage of water supply, especially load shedding of 20 hours in summers shuts down water pumping which affects the water supply. Although human being and state cannot change rate of rainfall, unfortunately, Pakistan has a decreasing trend of rainfall since last 16 years due to which drought is occurring and many individuals have lost their lives due to the scarcity of water. In addition, Pakistan is facing the shortage of water supply because of inadequate storage capacity. Pakistan did not build additional dams for water storage. The existing reservoirs have lost most of their storage capacity over the years due to sedimentation and silting. Furthermore, mismanagement and inadequate capacity of WASH institutions are also cause of the poor condition of these facilities and services in the country.

Sanitation is also vulnerable in urban and rural areas, in fact in the rural areas majority of the population has no sanitation services. Additionally, there are no standardized up to the mark industrial plants, in the country, for disposing and treatment of wastewater and solid. Moreover, the existing infrastructure such as waste carrier pipelines are damaged and defaulted, and leakage of wastewater occurs due to this poor infrastructure. As hygiene depends upon qualitative drinking water supply and sanitation services. However, the water-borne diseases are increasing day by day in Pakistan and health of the citizens of this country is

being badly affected due to a poor sanitation and water supply system which are requirements of better health. Almost 20% to 40% patients in the hospitals in Pakistan had been found suffering from diseases related to water and sanitation such as diarrhea, typhoid and hepatitis etc. (Mughal, 2011). In many cases, such diseases ultimately lead to death.

The Assistance of ADB and WB from 2000 to 2016

Pakistan as an economically frail state and having threats on its Eastern and Western territorial boundaries cannot spend a big chunk of its budget for development of WASH sector. However, Pakistan's regional and global development partners i.e. Asian Development Bank and World Bank are funding different projects for the development of WASH sector.

Efforts of ADB and WB in WASH sector of the “Punjab”

Punjab is the largest populated province of Pakistan. Due to employment opportunities, industrial development and availability of facilities in urban areas a large number of the population have migrated from backward areas of Punjab to urban areas, which in turn increased the urban population of Punjab and due to increase in population rate, deficiencies in urban services occurred. In the year 2000, only 45% of households had piped water supply connections. Although many urban centers have a sewerage system, the maintenance of this system was poor and the system itself was too old. However, these areas have been found to have a deficiency of plants to treat sewerage systems. The condition of rural areas of Punjab is worse than its urban areas, the majority of the population has no access to drinking water and they spend 15 minutes to 1 hour on daily basis in water fetching. Moreover, the water which is available is not hygienic. In rural areas, a large number of the population has no toilet facility. They performed open-air defecation, which further contaminates drinking water and creates diseases among them. Although, the literacy rate of Punjab is higher than other provinces, nonetheless, the majority is still unaware about health and hygiene practices and habits such as separation of water resources from animal and human feces, and purification of water through chlorination or boiling before drinking. Such a lack of awareness is also a major cause of water-related diseases.

The ADB and the WB had supported the province of Punjab through various projects during the year 2000 to 2016. The WB funded 1 project specifically for the province of Punjab, during the Musharraf era. Before this project of the WB, the government of Pakistan tried to improve water and sanitation condition. In 2001 devolution plan was launched by the government of Pakistan and under Devolution plan “Punjab Local Government Ordinance (PLGO)” was passed. This ordinance further established 5 District Governments and 144 Tehsil Municipal

Administrations (TMAs) for urbanization of the province of Punjab. However, as this was the first attempt by the government, so TMAs were not skilled and had lacked the required capacity to implement an urbanization plan. After the failure of the TMAs, the government of Pakistan called the WB for its assistance for the development of WASH sector. In the year 2006, in order to assist Pakistan, The WB approved 50.00 million USD for Punjab Municipal Services Improvement Project to improve urban services in the province with the involvement of the provincial government and TMAs (World Bank, 2014). Almost 30% of the amount had been used for water supply and 5% for waste-water collection and management. In the shadow of this mega project further 17 sub-projects were started for water sector with the cost of Rs. 1,501 million. Though improvement was recorded as a result of this project, however, the capacity of household water supply increased from 40% to 53% and the WB could not meet the 59 % target. Instead of the weakness of TMAs, the WB involved it for project implementation and inefficiency of TMAs led to delay in subprojects. However, after the completion of the project, the capacity of TMAs improved.

During the same era, the ADB financed 6 planned for WASH sector development in Punjab. In light of the ADB's (2000 to 2004) country's strategy of development of human resource and social infrastructure, Pakistan called the ADB in 2000 for technical assistance for the preparation of Southern Punjab Basic Urban Services Project. After fact-finding by the ADB this technical assistance (T. A) was approved in the year 2001 (Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2006). The total cost of T.A was 990,000 USD among which 800,000 USD was paid by the ADB and 190,000 USD by the government of Punjab. This technical assistance was for selected areas of Southern Punjab. The main purpose of this T.A was to evaluate the situation of water and sanitation in the selected areas of Southern Punjab. After an assessment of the WASH sector, in Punjab in the year 2003, the ADB approved two loans of the cost of USD 90 million for Southern Punjab Basic Urban Services Project (ADB, 2009). The aim of this project was to increase water supply through the construction of tube wells and the spread of water supply networks. There were 18 sub-projects for water supply, out of these 15 were completed on time in the year 2009 while 3 projects in Bahawalpur were completed in 2012 after project closing date in 2009. Moreover, for the sewerage water, almost 80 projects were started, these 80 projects consisted of disposal stations' construction, machinery for cleaning of wastewater and sewerage treatment plants. Among these 80 projects, 34 were completed within time, one project was dropped, and rest were completed after the closing date. At the closing of the project, only USD 51.5 million was disbursed and a heavy amount of the loan remains unutilized and underspent.

In the year 2009, the ADB provided T.A of USD 1 million for the preparation of Punjab Cities Improvement Investment Program (ADB, 2011). The aim of this assistance was to improve public-private partnership in order to improve urban

services delivery. In the year 2002 due to Khanpur Dam's poor yield and low efficiency of existing tube wells, the inhabitants of Rawalpindi could not get the supply of 256,000 cmd (cubic meter per day) which was planned for the Rawalpindi city. On the one hand the available water had poor quality although Water and Sanitation Agency(WASA) had installed chlorination system in some tube wells a large number of tube wells still did not have the chlorination facility. While on the other, there were no plants installed for disposal of sewerage, storm and industrial water. To improve the living environment of Rawalpindi, in the year 2003 the ADB decided to provide technical assistance to Rawalpindi Environmental Improvement Project (REIP) (ADB, 2003). This technical assistance covered design for the project, cost, financing plan and arrangements for implementation. Technical assistance is divided into two steps, the first step consists of following components such as analysis of the situation, analysis of water leakage from Rawal Lake water supply system and initiatives to stop the leakage and capacity building of WASA and tehsil municipal administration (TMA). While preparation of REIP was done in the second step. The total cost of the mentioned technical assistance was 438,000 USD. The ADB contribution was 350,000 USD, while the contribution of the government of Pakistan was 88,000 USD. After preparation of the Project, in 2005 ADB had started to provide assistance to REIP (ADB, 2011). This project consisted of different components such as sewerage treatment, water supply services, installation of the water meter, construction and rehabilitation of tube wells, and stormwater drainage etc. This project also consists of involvement of private sectors for urban services and institutional capacity building of institutions that will provide services related to management of water and waste. The total cost of this project was 85.7 million USD, where 60 million USD was issued by the ADB and rest was to be paid by the Punjab government, WASA and Rawal Town but only 19.6 million USD were utilized and out of 19.6 million USD 13.7 million USD were paid by the ADB and rest of the amount was paid by the government of the Punjab.

The overall performance of this project was not satisfactory, the output in the sewerage system and stormwater drainage was not up to mark because of poor design for these services and overlapping of Nullah Lai project. Although improvement in water supply has been occurred such as 26 tube wells are replaced and 25 old tube wells were rehabilitated. Again in 2014, ADB approved T.A of 1300,000 USD for Punjab Intermediate Cities Improvement Investment Program (ADB, 2016). This technical assistance by ADB covered the following areas such as assessment of the condition of urban services in selected 11 cities and formulation of Punjab.

Support for WASH Sector in Sindh

Sindh is the second largest province of Pakistan, however, its citizens from Thar

region to Karachi city are still facing acute shortage of water and sanitation services. Some of the reasons behind this serious problem are increasing population, poor governance and industrial zone which is polluting the Arabian sea every day through its chemical wastes. During the time frame of 2000 to 2016, there was no specific project by WB for WASH sector development in the region of Sindh. However, during the same year, the ADB sponsored 5 plans to improve the WASH facilities in the second largest province of the country.

In the year 2001, like Punjab, under the Sindh Local Government Ordinance, all responsibilities related to municipal services such as the supply of water and dispose of sewerage water and solid were handed over to the TMAs. However, due to lack of adequate funds and capacity, the TMAs could not perform satisfactorily. According to the need of time, the Government of Pakistan (GOP) requested to the ADB for technical assistance in the year 2002. The ADB sent a fact-finding team to Pakistan in 2004 in response to the request of the GOP. After the fact-finding, The ADB approved technical assistance for Sindh Basic Urban Services Project in the year 2007 (ADB, 2010). This technical assistance was basically for six towns of northern Sindh for preparation of projects for urban areas development. The total cost of this technical assistance was 995,000 USD, where 795,000USD was given by the ADB and it was the responsibility of the GOP to provide not only the remaining amount of 200,000 USD but accommodation, counter staff, transportation and workshop facilities as well.

In secondary towns of Sindh urban services such as drinking water supply, sanitation, and solid waste management in comparison to the number of residents are very rare. Locals of secondary cities have access to drinking water through pipelines only 2-4 hours in every 24 hours, while sanitary water carrier and disposal plants and pipelines are blocked and damaged. On the request of the GOP the ADB initiated MFF-Sindh Cities Improvement Investment Program in 2008 which is still active (ADB, 2014). The total cost of this program is USD 400 million where USD 300 million is given by ADB and USD100 million is contributed by the GOP. This financial support is divided into Tranche 1, Tranche 2, Tranche 3, Tranche 4 and Tranche 5. 16 % of this program is for the infrastructure of water supply while 15% share of this program is for wastewater management infrastructure and 63% is for reforms of those institutions which are performing services related to water supply, and solid waste management. The priority of this program is for the social sector of water supply, sanitation, and solid waste management, this project will improve lives of about 4 million residents and will provide social services to 570,000 households in secondary towns of Sindh. Most of the goals of this programs have been achieved, while some more objectives and will be achieved by building infrastructure for water services, wastewater management, and solid waste management through the extension of technical assistance to North Sindh Urban Services Corporation (NSUSC) which

is an implementing agency of the program. It also involved private sectors to improve the quality of services.

The ADB financed 38.00 million for Sindh Cities Improvement Investment Program Tranche-1 in 2008 (ADB, 2016). This program emphasized on the improvement of urban services such as water supply, sanitation and waste management of 6 towns of Sindh: Sukkur, Rohri, Larkana, New Sukkur, Shikarpur, and Khairpur. At the end of project completion pipeline connection increased from 37% to 45%. Performance of NSUSC as compared to its past capacity increased. Although, the overall improvement in Urban services was not up to mark as the project ending date was delayed for 6 months, however, 3 plants of water treatment and wastewater facilities were still not completed.

Northern-Sindh including areas of Ghotki and Jacobabad are covered for urban services in Sindh Cities Improvement Investment Program - Tranche 2 in 2012 which will remain active until the year 2017 (ADB, 2017). ADB financed 99.1 million USD for this project to raise the living standard of citizens by providing services of infrastructure for water supply, solid waste management, and wastewater. The main focus of this project is on infrastructure as highlighted by NSUSC. This Tranche did not show improvement in urban services of Sindh. Objections were raised by Supreme Court of Pakistan on different activities of NSUSC, due to the objection of the Supreme Court, the government of Sindh has halted some of the activities of the project which are still on hold.

Karachi is the hub of trade and economic activities, approximately 20% of national output is generated in this city. Almost 50% percent of the population is living below the poverty line. 40 % of the population in Karachi is living in Katchi Abbadis. People living in Katchi Abbadis' have limited access of social services and poverty has numerous dimensions over there, including unequal distribution of resources, no safety measures and inadequate access to public urban services of water supply and sanitation. Many people are compelled to use unhygienic water and dispose of their wastewater in open areas which in turn affects their health. In the year 2005, the GOP committed to raising the economic and social status of Karachi. It called upon the ADB for small-scale technical assistance (SSTA) for Mega City Project for the same purpose (ADB, 2005). An amount of almost 150,000 USD was given by the ADB for technical assistance. The purpose of technical assistance was to prepare megacity project in order to tackle multi-dimensional challenges including urban services issues of Karachi. Preparation of the first Mega City Development Project was initiated in the year 2005 for an estimated cost of 1.250 million USD. The ADB provided 1 million USD in the form of technical assistance, while the remaining amount was paid by the government of Sindh (ADB, 2005).

Assistance to WASH Sector of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) is the third largest province of Pakistan. The population of KP is facing many issues which include poor urban services such as inadequate access of drinking water and poor sanitation services, due to poor governance, weak capacity of implementing agencies, lack of information about urban problems and vulnerability of government to face disasters. From the year 2000 to the year 2016, both ADB and WB sponsored only one plan each for KP. The WB with the motto to improve living standards of residents of 586 communities, initiated a North-West Frontier Province (NWFP) Community Infrastructure Project II (NWFP CIP2) in 2004 (WB, 2010). The total approved amount of this project approved by WB was 32.20 million USD almost 46% of the said amount of the Bank's financing was for water and sanitation.

Under this project, 221 water schemes were started which consisted of the installation of water pumps on traditional wells, tube wells, and house connections. To improve sanitation system small drains were constructed which improved the lives of about 0.43 million inhabitants of the target area. Lack of information of the WB members and political influence affect the project, due to political influence some communities acquired more benefits as compared to others. Furthermore, the WB ignored the location demands and did not provide proper transportation and security to its officials which reveals lack of cooperation between the local government and the WB.

The ADB's new country partnership strategy (2015-19) towards Pakistan committed its support for urban development through improvement in infrastructure and capacity building of the institutions for water services, sanitation and by addressing other local and provincial level issues regarding urban development. Due to a strong political commitment by the government of KP, both the ADB and the GOP agreed for technical assistance to KP in 2016 (ADB, 2016). The technical assistance is particularly for water and other urban facilities and infrastructure development. The total cost of this project is USD 2.40 million, the Japan Fund for Poverty Reduction will pay USD 200 million while USD 0.40 million USD will be financed by the ADB. Other than this cost, expenditure of transport, counterpart staff, and workshops will be borne by the government of Pakistan. The technical assistance will prepare a roadmap for the development of the urban services and will increase the capacity of institutions which are responsible to provide these services.

Role of ADB and WB in WASH sector of Federally Administered Tribal Areas

The Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) of Pakistan where socio-economic development was already poor, the crises of militancy of 2009 made it

more vulnerable. To developed WASH sector in FATA, the WB in the era of 2000 to 2016 has supported 3 plans whereas the ADB has not funded specific project related to the WASH sector in this region.

To combat militancy in 2009, the government of Pakistan launched military operations in FATA and parts of KP which imposed an economic burden on the economy of Pakistan. Due to these operations, almost 3 million people were displaced from their localities which affected the social life of citizens. In the year 2012, on request of the government of Pakistan, the WB approved Fata Rural Livelihoods and Community Infrastructure Project (RLCIP) (WB, 2017). The approved amount for this project was USD 12 million, this project was especially for few agencies of FATA in order to rehabilitate social life of the affected locals by providing them social services. Almost 40% of this project was for general water, sanitation, and solid waste management. Approximately 240 infrastructure services which included water and sanitation were provided while the target was 451. The WB staff wanted to extend the project for 3 months for the process of additional financing, however, the FATA secretariat denied the extension. After hearing of this case in the High court, the secretariat was stopped from creating hurdle in work of the WB staff until the achievement of the project's objectives.

As the country's strategy partner, the WB in 2012 approved Fata Urban Centers Project (FUCP) (WB, 2012). Moreover, the WB approved USD 7.00 million for this project, 55% of this loan was for sanitation, water, and flood protection. The motive behind this project was to improve the condition of Khar town lies in the Bajaur Agency of FATA. Improvement in the water supply is one of the components of FUCP, under this project five tube wells of which three are run through solar energy and two are run through conventional methods have been constructed. Furthermore, two existing tube wells have been renewed. Moreover, almost 900 water connections were provided to the households to meet one of the objectives of the project.

However, the team of the project did not visit the location and had insufficient information regarding the FATA. Due to lack of the required knowledge about working environment in FATA, water and sanitation project was delayed four months and to fill this gap government of Pakistan issued USD 24,170. To support this project further in 2014, the WB approved additional funding of USD 1.00 million and about 30% of this additional funding was for water supply (WB, 2014). Where on the one hand this project was improving social services; construction work was affecting the environment through air, water and soil contamination on the other hand at the same time. However, there is no alternative to avoid the negative effect of this project.

WASH sector of Balochistan: The role of ADB & WB

Balochistan is the most unprivileged province of Pakistan, like other facilities of

life it also has inadequate water and sanitation facilities. A large number of the population have no access to clean drinking water and drains are open and even mixed with drinking water at some places. In addition, due to the lack of rainfall and water reservoirs, the storage capacity of this province is also quite poor. For water storage, the government of Pakistan, unfortunately, did not build any large or small dam that can store flood or rainwater. In these 16 years (2000-2016), there was no specific funding by the ADB or the WB for WASH sector of Balochistan, although some countrywide projects of the WB had covered WASH sector of Balochistan to up to some extent, however, keeping in view the severity of the problem in the province that work can be termed as negligible.

Epilogue

WASH sector is essential for any country's socio-economic development as it enhances human capital. In six administrative units of Pakistan, WASH sector is flimsy although the intensity of fragility varies from area to area. Although, both the ADB and the WB as development partners are funding for the development of this sector, however, some regions are gaining more privileges from this funding as compared to others.

From 2000 to 2016 the WB provided finance 8 times in this sector, for different projects in different regions of Pakistan. In these 16 years the WB, main projects were in the region of FATA, Punjab, KP, and only two projects were covering the whole of Pakistan. Moreover, the ADB has financed 12 times in forms of different loans such as technical assistance and multi-tranche finance facility etc. during the same era. In this era, Punjab, Sindh, and KP were main regions where the ADB was financing different projects of urban services. Meanwhile, Baluchistan has been completely fully ignored by the ADB and up to a large extent by the WB as well. Baluchistan is only included for subprojects of water and sanitation of Second Poverty Alleviation Fund Project by the WB.

Although projects of both these financial institutes have brought betterment in water supply and sanitation which led to betterment in human health, however, there were some loopholes in their strategies due to which targets of these projects were not achieved. For example, the WB is slow in fulfilling the prerequisites of the projects which lead to delay in projects. Mainly this negligence was done by the staff of the WB in Fata Urban Centers Project. The WB in its projects ignores demands of working environments and have less coordination with local government and this inadequate information and cooperation effects the smooth implementation of the project. Sometimes, WB overlooks the past poor performance of different project implementing agencies and time and again it involves the same weak agencies in its project implementation which effects projects performance the TMAs in Punjab is a point of reference for this claim.

Meanwhile, the ADB for many projects at first hand provides technical assistance and prepares a plan for project implementation, despite this strategy the ADB's projects did not complete within time and projects were closed prematurely, one example of this negligence is observed in Punjab Basic Urban Services Project. The factor of lack of information also exists in the ADB's strategies which leads to overlapping of projects such as in case of Rawalpindi Environmental Improvement Project.

The collaborative efforts of the government of Pakistan and the ADB and the WB have developed the WASH sector of Pakistan however, through by turning the insufficiencies of GOP and its institutes into fulfilling efficiencies this sector can become more advanced. The government and institutes should enhance interaction with each other so that the hurdles in the project implementation can be overcome and objectives of the project can be achieved.

The government of Pakistan should also extend its projects through institutes for underprivileged areas such as Balochistan because a country cannot get developed until all of its parts and units are developed simultaneously.

These financial institutes and GOP should incorporate the component of awareness in their projects because if the citizens are not aware of hygienic habits and about the importance of chlorinated water and proper sanitation, most of the investment in this sector will be wasted and would not be able to achieve the set goals.

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